

A Study on Ideals of an Integral Domain

Khin Nyein Aye*

Abstract

In this paper, we present the ideal structure of ring of quotients and localization at a prime ideal. Moreover, we describe the inverse of an invertible fractional ideal is unique. Finally, we present some properties of invertible ideals.

Keywords: Ring, field, ideal.

1. Multiplicative Subsets of a Quotient Ring

This section consists of some useful characterization of prime ideals and ring of quotients.

1.1 Definition. Let R be a ring and S be a nonempty subset of R that is closed under the operations of addition and multiplication in R . If S is itself a ring under these operations then S is called a *subring* of R . Let I be a subring of R . Then

I is said to be a *left ideal* if $r \in R$ and $x \in I \Rightarrow rx \in I$;

I is a *right ideal* if $r \in R$ and $x \in I \Rightarrow xr \in I$;

I is an *ideal* if it is both a left and right ideal.

1.2 Definition. An ideal P in a ring R is said to be a *prime ideal* if $P \neq R$ and for any ideals A, B in R

$$AB \subset P \Rightarrow A \subset P \text{ or } B \subset P.$$

1.3 Example. A zero ideal in any integral domain is a prime ideal since $ab = 0$ if and only if $a = 0$ or $b = 0$. If p is a prime integer, then the principal ideal (p) in the ring of integers Z is prime since

$$\begin{aligned} ab \in (p) \Rightarrow p \mid ab &\Rightarrow p \mid a \text{ or } p \mid b \\ &\Rightarrow a \in (p) \text{ or } b \in (p). \end{aligned}$$

Here is a very useful characterization of prime ideals.

1.4 Proposition. Let P be an ideal of a commutative ring R and $P \neq R$. Then the following statements are equivalent:

- (1) P is a prime ideal.
- (2) If for all elements $a, b \in R$, $ab \in P$ implies that either $a \in P$ or $b \in P$.

* Dr., Lecturer, Department of Mathematics, Bago University

Proof.(1) \Rightarrow (2) If P is any ideal and $ab \in P$, then the principal ideal (ab) is contained in P since P is a prime ideal. If R is a commutative ring, then $(a)(b) \subset (ab)$, whence $(a)(b) \subset P$. If P is prime, then either $(a) \subset P$ or $(b) \subset P$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1) Suppose that $AB \subset P$, where A and B are ideals of R . If $A \not\subset P$, then there is an element $a \in A$ with $a \notin P$. For every $b \in B$, $ab \in AB \subset P$ and so $b \in P$. Therefore, $B \subseteq P$. Thus P is a prime ideal.

1.5 Definition. An ideal M in a ring R is said to be *maximal* if $M \neq R$ and for every ideal N such that $M \subset N \subset R$, either $N = M$ or $N = R$.

1.6 Remark. If R is a commutative ring with identity, then every maximal ideal M in R is prime. The converse of above is false. For example, (0) is a prime ideal in the ring Z , but not a maximal ideal in Z .

1.7 Definition. If R is a ring with identity, we shall say that R is *quasi-local* if R has a unique maximal ideal; R is *semi-quasi-local* if R has only finitely many maximal ideals.

1.8 Definition. A nonempty subset S of a ring R is called a *multiplicatively closed set* if $a, b \in S \Rightarrow ab \in S$.

1.9 Examples.

- (1) The set of all nonzero elements in an integral domain is multiplicative set.
- (2) If P is a prime ideal in a commutative ring R , then both P and $S = R \setminus P$ are multiplicative sets.
- (3) The set of all nonzero integers is a multiplicative subset of ring of integers.

1.10 Definition. Let S be a multiplicatively closed set of a commutative ring R with identity. We define a relation on the set $R \times S$ by

$$(r, s) \sim (r', s') \Leftrightarrow s_1(rs' - r's) = 0 \text{ for some } s_1 \in S.$$

The relation \sim is an equivalence relation. The equivalence class of $(r, s) \in R \times S$ will be denoted by r/s . The set of all equivalence classes of $R \times S$ under the equivalence relation \sim will be denoted by $S^{-1}R$. The addition and multiplication on $S^{-1}R$ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} r/s + r'/s' &= (rs' + r's)/ss' & \text{and} \\ (r/s)(r'/s') &= rr'/ss'. \end{aligned}$$

Then $S^{-1}R$ is a commutative ring with identity and is called the *ring of quotients* or *ring of fractions* or *quotient ring* of R by S .

1.11 Theorem. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and S be a multiplicative closed set in R . Let $S^{-1}R$ be the set of equivalence classes r/s of $R \times S$ under the equivalence relation \sim .

- (1) If R is a nonzero ring with no zero divisors and $0 \notin S$, then $S^{-1}R$ is an integral domain.
- (2) If R is a nonzero ring with no zero divisors and S is the set of all nonzero elements of R , then $S^{-1}R$ is a field.

Proof. (1) We shall show that $S^{-1}R$ is an integral domain. We have known that if R is a commutative ring with identity and S is a multiplicatively closed subset of R , then $S^{-1}R$ is a commutative ring with identity. So we need to show that $S^{-1}R$ has no zero divisors. If R has no zero divisors and $0 \notin S$, then $r/s = 0/s$ if and only if $r = 0$ in R . Consequently, $(r/s)(r'/s') = 0$ in $S^{-1}R$ if and only if $rr' = 0$ in R . Since $rr' = 0$ if and only if $r = 0$ or $r' = 0$, it follows that $S^{-1}R$ is an integral domain.

(2) Suppose that R has no zero divisors and S is the set of nonzero elements of R . If $r \neq 0$, then the multiplicative inverse of $r/s \in S^{-1}R$ is $s/r \in S^{-1}R$. Therefore, $S^{-1}R$ is a field.

1.12 Example. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and Z be a ring of integers. If $R = Z$, then $S = \{3^n \mid n \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}\}$ is a multiplicatively closed set. Also, $S^{-1}R = \left\{ \frac{m}{3^n} \mid m \in Z, n \in \mathbb{N} \right\}$.

$2Z (= (2) \text{ in } Z)$ is an ideal in Z and $2S^{-1}Z (= (2) \text{ in } S^{-1}Z)$ is an ideal in $S^{-1}Z$.

2. The Extension of an Ideal in A Quotient Ring

In this section, we discuss how to use the quotient ring.

2.1 Definition. A function $f : R \rightarrow S$ is a **homomorphism** of rings if $f(a + b) = f(a) + f(b)$ and $f(ab) = f(a)f(b)$ for all $a, b \in R$. A **monomorphism** of rings is a homomorphism of rings which is an injective map. An **epimorphism** of rings is a homomorphism of rings which is a surjective map. An **isomorphism** of rings is a homomorphism of rings which is a bijective map.

2.2 Theorem. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and S be a multiplicatively closed subset of R .

(1) The map $\varphi_S : R \rightarrow S^{-1}R$ given by $r \rightarrow rs/s$ (for any $s \in S$) is a well-defined homomorphism of rings such that $\varphi_S(s)$ is a unit in $S^{-1}R$ for every $s \in S$.

(2) If $0 \notin S$ and S contains no zero divisors, then φ_S is a monomorphism.

(3) If R has an identity and S consists of units, then φ_S is an isomorphism.

Proof. To prove (1), it is obvious that, for any $s_1, s_2 \in S$,

$$rs_1/s_1 = rs_2/s_2.$$

Therefore, φ_S is well defined.

For any $r_1, r_2 \in R$ and any $s \in S$.

$$\begin{aligned}
\varphi_S(r_1) + \varphi_S(r_2) &= r_1s/s + r_2s/s \\
&= (r_1s^2 + r_2s^2)/s^2 \\
&= (r_1 + r_2)s^2/s^2 \\
&= \varphi_S(r_1 + r_2)
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\varphi_S(r_1)\varphi_S(r_2) &= (r_1s/s)(r_2s/s) \\
&= (r_1r_2)s^2/s^2 \\
&= \varphi_S(r_1r_2).
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\varphi_S(r)$ is a ring homomorphism.

For any $s \in S$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\varphi_S(s)(s/s^2) &= (s^2/s)(s/s^2) \\
&= s^3/s^3 \\
&= s/s \\
&= \text{the identity in } S^{-1}R,
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(s/s^2)\varphi_S(s) &= (s/s^2)(s^2/s) \\
&= s^3/s^3 \\
&= s/s \\
&= \text{the identity in } S^{-1}R.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\varphi_S(s)$ is a unit in $S^{-1}R$.

For the proof (2), suppose that φ_S is a monomorphism, $\varphi_S(r) = 0$ in $S^{-1}R$ for every $r \in R$.

Then $rs/s = 0_R/s$.

Therefore, $s_1(rs^2 - 0s) = 0_R$ for some $s_1 \in S$.

This implies that $rs_1s^2 = 0_R$.

By hypothesis, $s_1s^2 \in S$, $s_1s^2 \neq 0$ and s_1s^2 is not a zero divisor.

So we must have $r = 0$ and hence φ_S is a monomorphism.

To prove (3), suppose that R has an identity and S consists of units, it follows that $0 \notin S$ and S contains no zero divisors.

Therefore, by the result of (2), φ_S is a monomorphism.

To show that φ_S is an epimorphism, consider any $r/s \in S^{-1}R$.

By the hypothesis, s is a unit in R and so the inverse s^{-1} exists.

Now if we consider $rs^{-1} \in R$ we have

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_S(rs^{-1}) &= (rs^{-1})s/s \\ &= r/s.\end{aligned}$$

Let $r/s \in S^{-1}R$ with s is a unit in R . Then there exists $rs^{-1} \in R$ such that $\varphi_S(rs^{-1}) = rs^{-1}s/s = r/s$. Thus φ_S is an epimorphism and hence it is an isomorphism.

2.3 Definition. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and S be a multiplicative subset of R . If I is an ideal of R , then $S^{-1}I = \{a/s \mid a \in I, s \in S\}$ is an ideal in $S^{-1}R$ and it is called the *extension* of I in $S^{-1}R$.

The following theorem gives a sufficient condition for the equality of quotient ring of $S^{-1}R$ and $S^{-1}I$.

2.4 Theorem. Let R be a commutative ring with identity, S be a multiplicative subset of R and let I be an ideal of R . Then $S^{-1}I = S^{-1}R$ if $S \cap I \neq \emptyset$.

Proof: Suppose that

$$S \cap I \neq \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad s \in S \cap I.$$

We will show that

$$S^{-1}I = S^{-1}R.$$

Since $I \subset R$, $S^{-1}I \subset S^{-1}R$.

To show that $S^{-1}R \subset S^{-1}I$, consider any element $r_1/s_1 \in S^{-1}R$.

Since $s \in S \cap I$ and it is the identity in $S^{-1}R$.

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Now} \quad r_1/s_1 &= (r_1/s_1)(s/s) \\ &= r_1s/s_1s.\end{aligned}$$

Here $r_1s \in I$ since $s \in I$ which is an ideal of R .

Moreover $s_1s \in S$ since S is a multiplicative subset of R .

Therefore, $r_1/s_1 = r_1s/s_1s \in S^{-1}I$. This means that $S^{-1}R \subset S^{-1}I$ and hence $S^{-1}R = S^{-1}I$.

3. Localization of a Ring

This section deals with the localization at a prime ideal.

3.1 Definition. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and P a prime ideal of R . Then $S = R \setminus P$ is a multiplicatively closed subset of R . The ring of quotients $S^{-1}R$ is called the *localization of R at P* and is denoted by R_P . If I is an ideal in R , then the ideal $S^{-1}I$ in R_P is denoted by I_P .

3.2 Lemma. Let S be a multiplicatively closed subset of a commutative ring R with identity and let I be an ideal in R .

- (1) $I \subset \varphi_S^{-1}(S^{-1}I)$.
- (2) If $I = \varphi_S^{-1}(J)$ for some ideal J in $S^{-1}R$, then $S^{-1}I = J$. In other words, every ideal in $S^{-1}R$ is of the form $S^{-1}I$ for some ideal I in R .

Proof. (1) If $a \in I$, then $as \in I$ for every $s \in S$. Consequently, $\varphi_S(a) = as/s \in S^{-1}I$, whence $a \in \varphi_S^{-1}(S^{-1}I)$. Therefore, $I \subset \varphi_S^{-1}(S^{-1}I)$.

(2) Suppose that $I = \varphi_S^{-1}(J)$ for some ideal J in $S^{-1}R$. Then every element of $S^{-1}I$ is of the form r/s with $\varphi_S(r) \in J$. Hence

$$r/s = (1_R/s)(rs/s) = (1_R/s)\varphi_S(r) \in J.$$

Therefore, $S^{-1}I \subset J$. On the other hand, if $r/s \in J$, then

$$\varphi_S(r) = rs/s = (r/s)(s^2/s) \in J.$$

Hence $r \in \varphi_S^{-1}(J) = I$. Thus $r/s \in S^{-1}I$ and hence $J \subset S^{-1}I$. It follows that $S^{-1}I = J$.

3.3 Theorem. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and $S \subseteq R$ be a multiplicatively closed set of R . Let $\mathcal{U} = \{P / P \text{ is a prime ideal of } R, S \cap P = \emptyset\}$ and $\mathcal{V} = \{S^{-1}P / P \text{ is a prime ideal of } S^{-1}R\}$. Then there exists a bijection $\varphi: \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathcal{V}$, given by $P \mapsto S^{-1}P$.

Proof. Let $P \in \mathcal{U}$. Then P is a prime ideal of R and $P \cap S = \emptyset$. Then $S^{-1}P$ is a prime ideal in $S^{-1}R$ by Lemma 3.2. Therefore, $S^{-1}P \in \mathcal{V}$. It follows that $P \mapsto S^{-1}P$ defines an injective map $\varphi: \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathcal{V}$. We will show that φ is surjective. Let J be a prime ideal of $S^{-1}R$ and let $P = \varphi_S^{-1}(J)$. By Lemma 3.2(2), $S^{-1}P = J$. Now we will show that P is a prime ideal. Let $ab \in P$. Then $\varphi_S(ab) = \varphi_S(a)\varphi_S(b) \in J$ since φ_S is a homomorphism. Thus $\varphi_S(a) \in J$ or $\varphi_S(b) \in J$ since J is a prime ideal of $S^{-1}R$. Consequently, $a \in \varphi_S^{-1}(J)$ or $b \in \varphi_S^{-1}(J)$. So we get $a \in P$ or $b \in P$. Therefore, P is a prime ideal of R by Proposition 1.4. Hence $\varphi: \mathcal{U} \rightarrow \mathcal{V}$ is surjective.

3.4 Theorem. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and P be a prime ideal of R .

- (1) There is a one-to-one correspondence between the set of prime ideals of R which are contained in P and the set of prime ideal of R_P , given by $Q \mapsto Q_P$.
- (2) The ideal P_P in R_P is the unique maximal ideal of R_P .

Proof. (1) Since P is a prime ideal of R , $S = R \setminus P$ is a multiplicatively closed subset of R and $P \cap S = \emptyset$. By Theorem 3.3, there is a one-to-one correspondence between the set of prime ideals of R which are contained in P and the set of prime ideal of R_P , given by $Q \mapsto Q_P$.

(2) Let M be a maximal ideal of R_P . Since R_P is a commutative ring with identity, M is a prime ideal of R_P . Hence $M = Q_P$ for some prime ideal Q of R with $Q \subset P$. But $Q \subset P$ implies $Q_P \subset P_P$. Since $P_P \neq R_P$ by Theorem 2.4, we must have $Q_P = P_P$. Therefore, P_P is the unique maximal ideal in R_P .

3.5 Example. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and Z be a ring of integers. If $R = Z$, then $3Z$ is a prime ideal in Z .

$$\begin{aligned} R_{3Z} &= (R \setminus 3Z)^{-1} R \\ &= \left\{ \frac{m}{n} \mid m, n \in Z, 3 \nmid n \right\}. \text{ (localization of } R \text{ at } 3Z \text{).} \\ 3R_{3Z} &= \left\{ \frac{n}{m} \mid m, n \in Z, 3 \mid m, 3 \nmid n \right\} \text{ is a unique maximal ideal.} \end{aligned}$$

4. Properties of Invertible Ideals

In this section, we discuss the notation of fractional ideal and the concept of the invertibility of an ideal. Then we present the behavior of invertibility.

4.1 Definitions. Let R be an integral domain with quotient field K . A *fractional ideal* of R is a nonzero R -submodule I of K such that $rI \subset R$ for some nonzero $r \in R$. An ordinary ideal of R is a fractional ideal (take $r = 1$), and will often be referred to as an integral ideal.

For nonzero fractional ideals I and J of R , we define the *quotient*

$$(I : J) = \{x \in K \mid xJ \subseteq I\}.$$

It is an R -submodule of K and a fractional ideal of R .

4.2 Definition. Let R be a ring and $a \in R$. If $a \in R$ is not a zero divisor, then it is called a *regular element* of R .

4.3 Example. Every nonzero finitely generated R -submodules I of K is a fractional ideal of R .

$(A :_R B)$ is clearly an R -module. Suppose that b and d are regular elements of R such that $b \in B$ and $dA \subseteq R$. Then we have $bd(A :_R B) \subseteq dA \subseteq R$. Hence, $(A :_R B)$ is a fractional ideal of R . We also know that a fractional ideal of R is containing a regular element of R if and only if it contains a regular element of K , the total quotient ring of R .

The fractional ideal $(A :_R B)$ need not to be the same as $(A : B)$, since $(A : B)$ is defined as $(A : B) = \{a \in R \mid aB \subseteq A\} = (A :_R B) \cap R$.

We shall denote the set of all nonzero fractional of ideal of R by $\mathcal{F}(R)$.

4.4 Definition. A fractional ideal I of an integral domain R is said to be *invertible* if $IJ = R$ for some fractional ideal J of R .

4.5 Proposition. Let R be a ring and let K be its total quotient ring.

- (1) If $A \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ is invertible, then A contains a regular element of R and is finitely generated as an R -module.
- (2) Let $A, B \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ be such that $A \subseteq B$ and suppose that B is invertible. Then there exists an integral ideal C of R such that $A = BC$.
- (3) Let $A \in \mathcal{F}(R)$. Then A is invertible if and only if there exists $B \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ such that $AB = (d)$ for some regular element d of K .

Proof. (1) Let $B \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ be such that $AB = R$. So we have $1 = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i$ for some

$a_1, \dots, a_n \in A, b_1, \dots, b_n \in B$. Let $x \in A$ be arbitrary, then $xb_i \in AB = R$, hence $x = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i (xb_i)$.

So a_1, \dots, a_n generate A as an R -module. Now suppose that $dB \subseteq R$ for d ,

a regular element of R . Then $d \in dR = dAB = A(dB) \subseteq AR = A$. Thus A contains a regular element of R .

(2) Since B is invertible, there exists $B' \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ such that $BB' = R$. Set $C = AB'$, then since $A \subseteq B$, we have $C = AB' \subseteq BB' = R$. It follows that

$$BC = B(AB') = A(BB') = AR = A.$$

(3) Let x be a regular element of K and $B \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ be such that $AB = (x)$, then $A(Bx^{-1}) = R$, hence A invertible. If A is invertible, then there exists $C \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ such that $AC = R$. If $x \in K$ is a regular element of R , then $A(Cx) = (x)$, hence $B = Cx$ is the desired fractional ideal of R .

Let $A \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ be invertible, then by (1) of Proposition 4.5, we have $(R :_R A) \in \mathcal{F}(R)$.

4.6 Proposition. Let $A \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ be invertible and let $B \in \mathcal{F}(R)$ be such that $AB = R$, then $B = (R :_R A)$.

Proof. Since we have $AB = R$, then $B \subseteq (R :_R A)$. We also have $A(R :_R A) \subseteq R$ which implies that

$$(R :_R A) = R(R :_R A) = BA(R :_R A) \subseteq BR = B.$$

Hence $B = (R :_R A)$.

4.7 Proposition. Let R be an integral domain with quotient field K . The inverse of an invertible fractional ideal I is unique and is $I^{-1} = \{a \in K \mid aI \subset R\}$.

Proof. For any fractional ideal I the set $I^{-1} = \{a \in K \mid aI \subset R\}$ is easily seen to be a fractional ideal such that $I^{-1}I = II^{-1} \subset R$. If I is invertible and $IJ = JI = R$, then clearly $J \subset I^{-1}$. On the other hand, since I^{-1} and J are R -submodules of K , $I^{-1} = RI^{-1} = (JI)I^{-1} = J(II^{-1}) \subset JR = RJ \subset J$, whence $J = I^{-1}$.

4.8 Remarks. (1) If I, A, B are fractional ideals of R such that $IA = IB$ and I is invertible, then $A = RA = (I^{-1}I)A = I^{-1}(IB) = RB = B$.

(2) If I is an ordinary ideal in R , then $R \subset I^{-1}$.

(3) The ideal $I_1 I_2 \dots I_n$ is invertible if and only if each I_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n$) is invertible.

4.9 Example. Every nonzero principal ideal in an integral domain R is invertible. For, if K is the quotient field of R and $I = (b)$ with $b \neq 0$, let $J = Rc \subset K$ where $c = 1_R/b$. Then J is a fractional ideal of R such that $IJ = R$.

4.10 Proposition. Let R be a ring.

(1) If A, B , and C are ideals of R such that $A + B, B + C$ and $A + C$ are invertible, then $A + B + C$ is also invertible.

(2) If each ideal of R generated by two nonzero elements is invertible, then each ideal of R generated by a finite number of elements is invertible.

Proof. (1) $(A + B)(B + C)(A + C)$ is invertible by Remark 4.8 (3). Therefore, there exists a fractional ideal L of R such that

$$((A + B)(B + C)(A + C))L = R.$$

Since $(A + B)(B + C)(A + C) = (A + B + C)(AB + AC + BC)$,

$$(A + B + C)(AB + AC + BC)L = R.$$

Choose $(AB + AC + BC)L = J$. Then there exists a fractional ideal J such that

$$(A + B + C)J = R.$$

Thus, $A + B + C$ is invertible.

(2) We prove (2) by induction on the number of regular elements in a generating set for an ideal. Hence we assume that k is an integer greater than 1 such that each ideal of R generated by a set of k elements is invertible, and we consider a set $\{x_i\}_{i=1}^{k+1}$ of $k + 1$ regular elements of R . If $A = (x_1)$,

$B = (x_2, \dots, x_k)$, and if $C = (x_{k+1})$, then $A + B, B + C$ and $A + C$ are invertible. Therefore,

$A + B + C = (x_1, \dots, x_{k+1})$ is also invertible.

4.11 Theorem. Let R be an integral domain with quotient K . Any invertible ideal in a quasi-local domain is principal.

Proof. Let R be a quasi-local domain and I be an invertible ideal in R . Then $I^{-1}I = R$. Hence there exist $a_i \in I, b_i \in I^{-1}$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i = 1_R$. Thus one of them, say, $a_1 b_1$ is a unit. We deduce that $I = (a_1)$. Therefore, I is a principle ideal.

4.12 Theorem. Let R be an integral domain with a finite number of maximal ideals. Then any invertible ideal in R is principal.

Proof. Let M_1, \dots, M_n denote the maximal ideals in R , and let I be invertible. Since $II^{-1} = R$, for each i from 1 to n , we can find $a_i \in I$ and $b_i \in I^{-1}$ such that $a_i b_i \notin M_i$.

Moreover, M_i cannot contain the intersection of the remaining maximal ideals. Hence we can find an element u_i that is not in M_i but does lie in all the other maximal ideals.

Let $v = u_1 b_1 + \dots + u_n b_n$. Note that $v \in I^{-1}$ so that vI is an ideal in R .

We claim that vI lies in no maximal ideal. Suppose, for instance, that $vI \subset M_1$.

Then $va_1 \in M_1$. However, $va_1 = (u_1 b_1 + u_2 b_2 + \dots + u_n b_n) a_1$ and in this expression $u_1 b_1 a_1 \notin M_1$ while all other terms lies in M_1 . Hence $vI \subset M_1$ is impossible. We have proved $vI = R$ and $I = (v^{-1})$ is principal.

We proceed to the behavior of invertibility under localization.

4.13 Theorem. Let I be an invertible ideal in an integral domain R , and let S be a multiplicatively closed set in R . Then I_S is invertible in R_S .

Proof. Since I is an invertible ideal in R , $II^{-1} = R$ and hence $(II^{-1})_S = R_S$. We have $(II^{-1})_S = I_S I_S^{-1}$. Thus $R_S = I_S I_S^{-1}$. Therefore, I_S is invertible in R_S .

4.14 Theorem. Let I be a finitely generated ideal in an integral domain R . Then I is invertible if and only if I_M is principal for every maximal ideal M .

Proof. If I is invertible then I_M is invertible by Theorem 4.13 and hence principal by Theorem 4.11. Conversely, assume that each I_M is principal. If $II^{-1} \neq R$, embed it in a maximal ideal M . In R_M , by hypothesis, I_M is principal. The generator can be selected to be an element i of I . Let a_1, \dots, a_n be generators of I . We have $s_j a_j \in (i)$ for any elements $s_j \in R$, $s_j \notin M$. Write $s = s_1 \dots s_n$. Then si^{-1} throws all the a_j 's into R , whence $si^{-1} \in I^{-1}$. But now, $s = si^{-1}i \in I^{-1}I \subset M$ is a contradiction.

Conclusion

We have discussed the some concepts of ideals. And then, we proceed to the behavior of invertibility under localization which constitutes an important class of ideals in today's mathematics.

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